

SIMULATED ACTIVE FLOW CONTROL IN A VARTM PROCESS USING LOCALIZED INDUCTION HEATING

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Unpredictable variabilities in preform permeability can lead to the formation of dry spots and nonuniform flow progression during mold filling in the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. A real time flow control is often required to achieve complete and void-free fill. This control is often designed around controlling the inlet pressures or flow rates and has been shown in the literature to be limited in its ability to steer the flow in regions far from the inlet ports. A viable solution explored in this paper toward addressing this problem is that of localized heating of the resin during the mold filling process. Localized heating can reduce the viscosity of the flowing resin and potentially compensate for preform permeability variation throughout the mold. In this paper localized heating is achieved using an induction heater with carbon fiber susceptors embedded in the preform layup. This type of control must be applied to the VARTM process in such a way as to heat in the lagging regions while avoiding overheating and thus prematurely curing the resin. To this end, this paper presents a real time control strategy for localized induction heating of the flowing resin during the VARTM process. This strategy is implemented in a simulation framework, using a process model for nonisothermal flow simulation of the VARTM process in the presence of induction heating. A standard VARTM molding setup is augmented by a CCD camera that gathers real time flow front information, which is used by the computerized control to determine the ideal location and power level for the induction coil that is then moved by means of motorized stages. Process simulations are conducted using the model of this setup to evaluate different techniques of coil movement and find methods that achieve the best real time flow controlled, localized heating. The active control based on localized heating on demand is shown to be successful in reducing the flow lags in regions of relatively low permeability, thus improving the uniformity of the flow during mold filling. Details of the control scheme and additive results will be presented and discussed.

KEYWORDS: Induction Heating, Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM), Flow simulations, Active Control, Permeability Variations

INTRODUCTION

VARTM is an attractive and affordable method of producing large-scale composite structures. As is common across liquid molding processes, in general, part defects often arise during the mold filling stage of this process, where a reactive resin is drawn into a porous preform placed in a single hard sided mold through the use of vacuum. As the resin is drawn through the preform by the pressure gradient, the fluid preferentially follows the path of least resistance governed by its viscosity and the permeability of the preform material. The relation between flow velocities, permeability, pressure gradient, and viscosity is governed by Darcy's law [1, 2]. Designing the process so as to achieve uniform and complete fiber saturation is imperative for fabricating quality components. Furthermore, despite an optimum process design, process and material parameter uncertainty as well as real time and run-to-run variations can cause deviations from the design targets [3]. Robust fabrication therefore calls for on-line and real time control strategies that ensure reliable fill in the face of practical variabilities.

Previous work has been done on control of resin transfer molding processes. Nielsen and Pitchumani [4]–[6] presented model-based control schemes for the resin transfer molding process, including controls for both flow rate controlled and pressure controlled injection systems. They used neural networks [4, 6] and real time process model simulations [5] to actively control the RTM process. One of the control strategies used online permeability estimation using fuzzy logic theory [6]. The control schemes were shown to steer the flow and reproduce multiple desired fill patterns reliably and in the face of permeability uncertainty. Walsh and Mohan [7] reported a control approach of changing resin inlet locations mid fill as a means of compensating for low permeability in the VARTM process. Real-time flow sensing was used to determine the optimum time to activate the second resin inlet. Heider, et al., [8] developed a feedback controlled VARTM test bed that uses both cameras and a SMARTweave flow sensing along with an actively controlled vacuum system.

The conventional control parameters in a control scheme are the inlet pressures or flow rates in the case of RTM (equivalently the vacuum levels in VARTM). These parameters are varied interactively with the filling process to steer the flow through the mold in a desired fashion. It is commonly recognized that the flow controllability via injection port based control diminishes as the flow front moves away from the controlled boundary [4]. This becomes especially evident in the case of heterogeneous preforms, where it can become difficult to uniformly fill a low permeability patch region located away from the inlet port. This situation can potentially lead to dry spots and wasted parts, despite the presence of an injection port-based control scheme.

The goal of this research is to develop and implement an active control scheme that uses localized heating to compensate for permeability variations in the preform. To this end, this paper builds upon previous reported work on this topic by the authors [9, 10], to utilize the numerical process model as a tool for testing an active control scheme. Localized volumetric heating is produced by induction heating of carbon weave susceptors embedded within the preform. The control of this volumetric heating includes two dimensional motion as well as induction coil voltage variation with the goal of improving the uniformity of flow fronts while limiting material temperatures.

The next section describes the numerical model used to simulate the process. The active control section describes the architecture of the control scheme. Results of detailed studies using the process simulation model along with the active control are presented and discussed in the results section.

NUMERICAL PROCESS MODEL

The mold filling with induction heating includes multiple physical phenomena, which must be modeled for a comprehensive process simulation. These include: viscous flow through a permeable material, preform permeability variation due to compaction, electromagnetically-induced current flow which leads to resistive volumetric heating, material property variation due to temperature change, and both conduction and convection heat transfer. The numerical formulation consists of solving the continuity equation combined with Darcy's law to relate the flow velocities and the pressure gradients within the mold. The non-isothermal effects are considered by solving the energy equation where the induction heating is represented by a volumetric source term. The strong dependence of viscosity on temperature creates a coupling of these governing equations, which are solved to obtain the temperature and flow fields simultaneously. The volumetric source term created by the induction heating is derived from the current flow through the susceptor grid and the electrical resistance of that grid segment. This requires evaluation of the induced current in the susceptor grid, which is related to the induced electromotive force (*emf*) in a closed loop of the grid. The magnetic field generated by the coil, which is governed by the Biot-Savart law, is used to calculate the induced *emf*. In the present model, the resin cure kinetics is not considered, but will be included in a future study.

In the interest of brevity, details of the mathematical formulation and the numerical simulation procedure are not described here. The interested reader is referred to [9,10] for explicit details of the numerical model used here and to [1, 2, 11–19] for additional information. In brief, the process model includes: a two-dimensional flow model solving Darcy’s law, where permeability values are calculated using a heterogeneous compaction model, a three-dimensional heat transfer model with an induction heating analysis used as the source of volumetric heat generation, and a temperature-dependent viscosity model, based on the experimental glycerin and water working fluid, that couples the flow and heat transfer models. The process model is applied to the $30.5\text{cm} \times 30.5\text{cm}$ mold shown in the schematic of the experimental setup (Fig. 1). This schematic shows a standard VARTM setup with the augmented induction heating control equipment including an induction heater, x-y motorized stages used to move the induction coil and a CCD camera used to feedback flow front information.

Fig. 1: (a) A close up view of the mold cross section showing the mold, preform, and carbon susceptor mat sections, and (b) a schematic of the modeled setup.

ACTIVE CONTROL

The active control of induction heating in the VARTM process, as seen in Fig. 1, has two main requirements: voltage and motion control. Induction coil voltage must be varied to provide significant aid for flow permeation in low permeability areas while ensuring that material temperatures are limited so as not to prematurely start the cure reaction. The induction coil must also be moved to insure that heating is applied to appropriate regions of the molded part. In the following studies, only x and y motion are considered. The induction coil remains fixed in the z direction so as to maintain a constant coil-susceptor gap during molding of the flat part considered here. The following text will describe individually, for the control scheme presented here, the method of limiting the material temperatures by varying the induction coil voltage, and the methods used for motion control in the x and y directions.

Induction coil voltage control

A fundamental challenge of the chosen heating control method is that material temperatures must be limited so as not to gel the resin during the filling stage of the process. To this end, an upper bound for material temperature is specified as 100°C in this study, so as to limit the degree of crosslinking. Future

studies will relax this assumption and replace the upper processing bound with a function of the resin cure kinetics. It is not practical to feedback material temperatures from within the molded part, where the maximum material temperatures occur, since the temperature sensor will interfere with, and will be influenced by induction heating. Therefore, a feedforward scheme has been developed which solves a simplified energy equation to quickly estimate material temperatures.

In the control scheme studied here, it is sought to maximize the induction coil voltage and thus achieve the fastest fill times and when combined with appropriate coil motion the objective is to achieve uniform flow progression throughout the fill. Estimated temperatures from the model described below are used to choose the induction coil voltage that maximizes the temperature without surpassing the upper bound.

The energy equation solved in this feedforward scheme is based on the lumped capacitance method, and is written as follows:

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = -c_f h(T - T_\infty) + q''' \quad (1)$$

The left hand side is the transient temperature term, while on the right hand side, the first term describes convection heat transfer [12] and the last term is the heat generation term that is dependent on the induction coil voltage. In this equation h is the convection heat transfer coefficient T is the temperature and T_∞ is the ambient temperature. The coefficient c_f is a correction factor that will be described later. Eq. 1 is analytically solvable for either the coil voltage or the material temperature, when combined with the induction heating model, if given the material temperature or coil voltage respectively. In a given control interval, Eq. 1 is used to estimate the current material temperatures, using the induction coil voltage and location determined in the previous control interval, at every individual x, y location (Fig. 1) as segmented by the numerical mesh. Next, the new induction coil voltage is determined using the newly determined coil location, and the specified upper temperature bounds. This calculation is also done at every segmented x, y location in the vicinity of the induction coil and the minimum calculated voltage is used during the next control interval.

The c_f term in Eq. 1 is a correction factor that replaces the surface area term usually found in its place. This term was used to compensate for the following simplifying assumptions: uniform temperature through the thickness, negligible conduction in every direction, and negligible advection. A value of $c_f = .45$ was found to most closely fit the analytical solution to the experimentally validated numerical model presented in section two [10]. The solid lines in Fig. 2 show the analytical solution to Eq. 1 for various induction coil voltages, while the individual data points represent the numerical solution at the same representative x, y position under the induction coil for the same induction coil voltages. Each simulation was run with a static coil location relative to the fluid flow and a constant voltage to obtain the temperature time trace. Fig. 2 shows a strong correlation between the analytical and numerical approaches especially as time increases. This simple feed forward temperature control scheme is capable of limiting the maximum temperatures to within 20°C of the desired upper bound.

Motion control: y-direction

It is desired here to develop a generalized control strategy that can be applied to any preform layout even where the layout geometry is not known *a priori*. To that end, knowledge gained in previous studies [10], that heating ahead of a low permeability area can cause the flow to follow the path of least resistance and go around the low permeability area entirely, is used to generate the y -motion (motion along the global flow direction, Fig. 1) strategy explored here. The induction coil always follows the flow front, lagging just enough to not heat any unfilled areas.

Fig. 2: Material temperatures for a stationary coil heating of a filled mold from numerical simulations (data points) and from simplified analytical solution (solid lines).

Motion control: x-direction

The desired motion of the coil in the x -direction is to supply heating to areas lagging behind the mean flow front. The exact positioning of these areas is determined by the preform layup, but in order to insure that the control can handle unknown layups, this coil position must be determined from the flow front feedback. The control calculates the percent fill in the y -direction for every group of four adjacent grids across the width (x direction) of the mold. The location of the minimum calculated value, or maximum lag, is taken as the desired coil x location for that control interval.

Fig. 3: Preform layup geometries used in the numerical studies involving flow front following schemes: (a) center patch layup, (b) computer generated random layup.

The only desired heating areas across the width of the mold are those determined as stated above. Following this logic, the induction coil is turned off during its transit in the x direction to the target location, and is supplied voltage only while above the desired location. However, since the flow front lag, and therefore the desired heating location, changes dynamically during the process, a minimum residence (delay) time at the target location must be specified so as to avoid undesirable scenarios such as the coil leaving the target spot prematurely, or the coil constantly chasing the maximum flow lag while never stopping to heat. Since the induction heater in the experimental setup takes seven seconds to energize from standby to a full 200 V, it is impractical to move the coil to a location and heat for any

duration less than 7 sec. Under this scheme, the coil will be delayed by a predetermined amount of residence time at each identified heating position across the mold width, where it will heat as prescribed by the temperature bounds presented above. At the end of this delay, the control scheme determines the next desired heating location. Studies were carried out for delay times of 0, 2, 5, 10, and 15 seconds using the preform layups illustrated in fig. 3, which are described in detail in the next section. Results of these studies are presented in the following section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All results presented in this section utilize the root mean squared (RMS) error as a measure of the flow front uniformity. Fig. 4 is a graphic representation of the RMS error

Fig. 4: Schematic of RMS error, ϵ_{RMS} , definition.

definition. The gray area represents the filled region of the mold and the white region is the unfilled region at one point in time during the fill. The dashed horizontal line represents the ideal desired flow front location. For all of the studies considered here, this ideal was defined as the mean fill value across the width. A value of δ_i was calculated at every grid point across the width of the mold. This value represents the difference between the ideal and actual flow fronts. In fig. 4 the difference is shown as the hatched area. The RMS error

Fig. 5: Center low permeability patch layup results: (a) Time traces of RMS error, ϵ_{RMS} , for five delay times and the unheated case. Flow progression with time (dashed line) and overlaid coil trace (solid line) for (b) Unheated case, and (c) Five second delay time.

was then calculated by the following equation:

$$\varepsilon_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i^2}{N}} \quad (2)$$

A series of studies were conducted using this front following scheme and the preform layups presented in fig. 3. The layups in fig. 3 are based on segmenting the mold with a 4x4 grid and choosing different permeabilities for each segment. Fig. 3(a) has low permeability segments in the center four spaces and represents a practical application of this type of control. Fig. 3(b) places a variety of permeabilities in computer selected random locations. Permeability values in Fig. 3 are represented by the Carman Kozeny coefficients used in the numerical modeling.

Studies were run for both of these layups with heating delay times as described in the active control section of 0, 2, 5, 10, and 15 seconds. The goal of this study is to determine the effectiveness of the flow following strategy and also to determine an optimum delay time for a generalized control that is independent of preform layup. Figs. 5–6 correspond to the preform layups shown in figs. 3(a)-3(b). In each of figs. 5-6, frame (a) is a time trace of the RMS error, ε_{RMS} , for all five delay times as well as the unheated case, frame (b) is a plot of the flow fronts over time for the unheated case, and frame (c) is a plot of the flow fronts for the best delay time, which varies with each preform layup. Also shown in frame (c) of each figure is a trace of the center of the induction coil during the fill.

It can be seen in figs. 5–6 that variation due to delay time in the ending RMS error is minimal. All of the layups show large improvement between their unheated (worst) cases, (b) and the actively controlled cases in frame (c). For the central patch, (figs. 3(a) and 5) the control maintains the coil in the central region of the mold width as expected, while following the flow front in the y direction. Similarly, for the random layup (figs. 3(b) and 6) the coil spends the majority of it's time over the low permeability regions.

Fig. 6: Computer generated random layup results: (a) Time traces of RMS error, ε_{RMS} , for five delay times and the unheated case. Flow progression with time (dashed line) and overlaid coil trace (solid line) for (b) Unheated case, and (c) Ten second delay time.

Fig. 7 is a bar graph representing the ending RMS errors, ε_{RMS}^* , for the cases presented in figs. 5–6. On the x axis the studies are grouped by preform layup and within each group, the ending RMS errors for the various delay times are presented. For comparison, all RMS errors have been nondimensionalized by their unheated counterparts. The center layup shows five seconds as the ideal delay time and the computer generated random layup shows ten seconds as the ideal delay. As mentioned above, the practical lower limit for the delay is seven seconds, so this data leads to a recommendation of a 7–10 second delay for any unknown preform layup although further studies must be done to confirm this.

Ongoing work explores the control strategy for a variety of other preform layups and on implementation of the active control derived here in the actual experimental setup. These will be reported in the future.

Fig. 7: Ending RMS error, ε_{RMS}^* , nondimensionalized to the unheated case, for five preform layups and five heating delay times, with the longitudinal motion of the coil following the flow front.

CONCLUSIONS

Studies on a scheme for motion and voltage control of an induction coil, and the resulting viscosity reduction, as a method of compensating for permeability variation and increasing flow uniformity in the VARTM process were investigated. A numerical process model was used in control simulations to evaluate the performance of the control scheme. The width-wise motion was found to be ideal if it was delayed at the desired heating locations by 7 to 10 seconds to allow for adequate residence time for flow improvement. The length-wise coil motion was found to heat desired regions if a flow front following scheme was adopted. Temperatures were limited to a preset upper bound through the use of a simplified energy balance equation. This equation was used to estimate material temperatures and predict future coil voltages that would limit maximum material temperatures below the dictated upper bound. Overall this control scheme was found capable of reducing the ending RMS error of the investigated mold fills by 40% to 88% of uncontrolled equivalent fills all while limiting material temperatures to within 20° of the desired upper bound.

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REFERENCES

1. Advani S. Flow and rheology in polymer composites manufacturing. New York: Elsevier, 1994.
2. Parnas R. Liquid composite molding. Munich: Hanser, 2000.
3. Padmanabhan S. and Pitchumani R. Stochastic modeling of nonisothermal flow during resin transfer molding processes. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 1999;42(16):3057–3070.
4. Nielsen D, Pitchumani R. Intelligent model-based control of preform permeation in liquid composite molding processes, with online optimization. *Composites A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2001;32(12):1789–1803.
5. Nielsen D, Pitchumani R. Closed-loop flow control in resin transfer molding using real-time numerical process simulations. *Composites Science and Technology* 2002;62(2):283–298.
6. Nielsen D, Pitchumani R. Control of flow in resin transfer molding with real-time preform permeability estimation. *Polymer Composites*, In Press 2002.
7. Walsh S, Mohan R. Sensor-based control of flow fronts in vacuum-assisted RTM. *Plastics Engineering* 1999; 55(10):29–32.
8. Heider D, Graf A, Fink B, Gillespie J. Feedback control of the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. *SPIE Conference on Process Control and Sensors for Manufacturing*. California, USA: 1999. pp.133–141.
9. Johnson R, Pitchumani R. in *Proceedings of the 34th International SAMPE technical conference*. Maryland, USA: 2002; 34(1):250–261.
10. Johnson R, Pitchumani R. Enhancement of Flow in VARTM using localized induction heating. *Composites Science and Technology* 2003; Accepted for publication.
11. Han K, Jiang S, Zhang C, Wang B. Flow modeling and simulation of SCRIMP for composites manufacturing. *Composites A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2000;31(1):79–86.
12. Incropera F, DeWitt D. *Fundamentals of heat and mass transfer*, fourth edition. New York: Wiley, 1996.
13. Schaffer J, Saxena A, Antolovich S, Sanders T, Warner S. *The science and design of engineering materials*. Second edition. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1999.
14. Serway R. *Physics for scientists and engineers*. Forth edition. Chicago: Saunders College Publishing, 1996.
15. Yarlagadda S, Fink B, Gillespie J. Resistive susceptor design for uniform heating during induction bonding of composites. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials* 1998;11(4):321–337.
16. Irwin J, Kerns D. *Introduction to electrical engineering*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1995.
17. Anderson D, Tannehill J, Pletcher R. *Computational fluid mechanics and heat transfer*. New York: Hemisphere Publishing, 1984.
18. Chan A, Hwang S. Modeling non-isothermal impregnation of fibrous media with reactive polymer resin. *Polymer Composites* 1992;310(32).
19. Guan X, Pitchumani R. Viscous fingering in a Hele-Shaw cell with finite viscosity ratio. *ASME Journal of Fluids Engineering*, 2003;125(2):354–364.